

Research Article

<p>MEDIA COMMUNICATION</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Social Sciences</p> <p>Keywords: semiotics, media text, media discourse, mediallynguistics, paralinguistic means, hypertext, creolization, creolithic text.</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p> <p>The present article is devoted to the exploration of modern forms of communication and the mediallynguistic features of Internet communication. The essence of paralinguistic means in the formation of media text and media discourse is revealed.</p>		

The Internet is a technical opportunity that shows how a person understands the real world, how he perceives the information space between the universe and man. Cognitiveness, on the other hand, as an intrinsic feature of speech, determines the extent to which the human mind perceives the information transmitted in Internet communication. The rapid emergence of Internet communication as a major phenomenon has necessitated the study of processes aimed at optimizing the perception of information by users. The fact that the multidimensional media text used so far in radio and television is freely used by any communicator in the Internet space, the study of Internet communication texts on the basis of modern methods of analysis also takes into account the compositional features of the media text.

Modern forms of Internet communication, which mean a combination of linguistic and paralinguistic means belonging to different semiotic systems, are characterized by terms such as semiotic complex, unconventional, mixed, polycode, creolized, or creolithic, multi-text. S.Y. Koltysheva, E. V. Gorina, O. A. Nikitina, O. A. Gudkova, F. Zander, E. Y. Raspopina, E. N. Galichkina, E. E. Anisimova, A. A. Bernatskaya, N. D. Tsyganova, Yu. A. Sorokin, E. F. Tarasov, L. V. Dubovitskaya and others use creolized text, while L. L. Sandler, E. V. Babich, V. A. Sentsova, A. S. Bovshik, L. S. Bolshakovas use polycode text terms. It is obvious that the study of the role and importance of the virtual world in human and social life is equally important for linguists, psychologists, sociologists. This concept is just entering Uzbek linguistics [25; 1].

It should be noted at this point that the concept of hypertext, which is close to the above terms, implies a completely different phenomenon. “Connection to another source by nonlinear connection with a special link in a multidimensional space” [15]. Scientists have done a lot of research on this, and in 1989 T. Berners-Lee developed **html (HTML - Hypertext Mark Up Language)**, a language for marking hypertext, and created a convenient way to refer to another source. This process can be likened to reading a written text book and searching for information from another book, whether an additional dictionary or the like, where needed. On the Internet, this can be done by clicking on a single link. The fact is that the Internet has a huge potential as the most convenient means of obtaining information and a source of hyperbase. In particular, the

user working on the text has the opportunity to enter other information space, such as a dictionary, e-book, through special links, and get enough information from it on the topic of interest. This is a very convenient opportunity for students, professionals in a particular field, or a volunteer seeker. Hence, the concepts of **hypertext and mixed semiotic text** (information) represent different processes.

A new stage of anthropocentric relations – (virtual) communicative space – the communicative-semiotic parameters of Internet communication require the study of changes in the semiotic features and functions of information transmission.

The modern technical base has led to the formation of specific features of virtual communication, the expansion of the possibilities of the communication space, and ultimately the information carrier has become one of the members of communication. A special communication channel allows communication between communicators that are far apart. Interlocutors include a network of at least two computers (or telephones) and a certain number of elements. Data entered by the addressee as text, image, audio or video file is encoded and transmitted over the digital technical network, then decoded again in the original on the addressee's computer (phone). Thus, electronic communication mediation determines the properties of the electronic substrate [2].

“Virtual communication has changed the nature of speech - letters and words, sounds and images, the human body and things have been replaced by numbers, so they are virtual and therefore they have such unique capabilities” [6, p. 26].

The semiotic features of the character are reflected in the change in the nature and intensity of text creolization in virtual communication. Creolization is a combination of linguistic and paralinguistic means. With the use of multimedia components in the communication process, the degree of creolization, the capacity of the substrate is increasing.

So how did the term **creolization** come about? It is well known that in Western linguistics there is a lot of research on the concept of *creole languages*, because the term describes one of the specific forms of the process of emergence of new languages in the world.

Creole language. According to TA Imomnazarov, native people and colonialists in the colonial countries used French, Spanish, and Portuguese to communicate with Europeans of many different ethnic groups and black slaves from Africa who live and work side by side, whom colonialists brought with themselves. In this case, the language of the state that colonized the territory serves as an intermediary language. During mass language learning, learners pronounce European languages based on sounds in their native languages. Thus, on the basis of European languages, new languages emerged, which were similar to them but different [12, p.12].

The dictionary “Explanatory dictionary of the Russian language” by SI Ojegov and N.Yu. Shvedova gives a different definition: Creole. 1. The first generation of colonizers - immigrants

from Europe (Spain, Portugal) to South America. 2. In the Aleutian Islands and Alaska in the XVIII-XIX centuries: born from a mixed marriage of Russians with Aleutians, Eskimos or Indians [19, p.748].

According to many, the word “**creole**” is derived from the Spanish verb *creare* – to create, to give birth. Either way, it is assumed that it is formed from the intermingling of non-related languages belonging to different ethnic groups. From the point of view of the essence of the matter, by the XXI century, the term Creolithic text was formed. Texts formed from a mixed use of linguistic and paralinguistic symbols are called creolized or creolithic text. The concept of creolithic text was first introduced in 1990 by Yu. A. Sorokin and E. F. Tarasov [22, p.180].

At this point, we will focus in detail on the paralinguistic means that are no less important than language units in the **creolithic texts** widely used in the modern system of communication. Paralinguistics is derived from the Latin words **para** – ‘adjacent’, **lingua** – ‘language’, which means “adjacent to the language”, “used in conjunction with the language.” This term was first proposed by A. Hill. Later, J. Treyger wrote a special work in this field, substantiating its essence [18, p. 170].

Paralinguistic tools, as an auxiliary system of important communicative importance in the process of communication, help to more fully ensure the functional features of language units, methodological coloring, “depending on the situation, to standardize speech, in particular, to concisely express the purpose of the addressee” [13, p.18].

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The rapid growth of visual information in modern communication has aroused the natural interest of linguists in paralinguistic, i.e., nonverbal means used in conjunction with written speech. Paralinguistic tools began to attract the attention of linguists in the 1920s. Initially, the focus was on graphic tools only in cases related to the study of the level of technical and aesthetic characteristics of publications as paralinguistic means of written communication. While the first phase envisioned features related to fiction, their systematic study only began in the 1970s. The first methodological research was conducted by the author on the expressive capabilities of these tools, ensuring the integrity of the methodological features of the work of art, their role in the implementation of the artistic idea. At present, paralinguistic tools, their content and pragmatic possibilities are being intensively studied.

Addressing to paralinguistics in textual linguistics has arisen due to the need to identify the tools involved in the search for improved forms of text creation, to achieve a more complete pragmatic effect of the text on the addressee.

Based on the study of scientific sources and taking into account the vast possibilities of the development of computer technology in the creation of text, we have classified paralinguistic tools as follows:

I. Paralinguistic means of speech (also commonly referred to as nonverbal means):

1. **Phonation means:** sound timbre, tone, pause, highlighting the desired places by changing the sound;

2. **Optical means:** eye signals;

3. **Facial expressions:** facial movements;

4. **Kinetic or “pantomime” means:** head and body movements [7, p.32].

Instead of these paralinguistic tools that accompany oral speech, media such as emoticons, emojis, gifs are used in virtual communication.

II. Paralinguistic means of written and virtual communication:

1. **Graphic tools:**

a) non-traditional use of punctuation marks on the basis of methodological requirements;

b) change the size and color of the font, highlight italics;

c) auxiliary symbolic graphic symbols: §, №, %, +, -, /, [], &, \$, *, =;

2. **iconic (pictorial) means:** such as picture, photo, scheme, drawing, table;

3. **audiovisual means:** such as audio recording, video recording.

Within the framework of the creolithic text concept of Internet communication, the concepts of **media text, media discourse, mass media, multimedia** are intertwined. The need to study such multifaceted issues as the universal and specific aspects of these concepts, their interrelationships, the role of one in the formation of the other, the role of national and global dialogue in development, poses important challenges for our researchers. That is why in a short period of time a field of research has been formed in a number of new directions, and the astonishing ‘conquest’ of humanity by the "media space" has aroused the interest of all.

In linguistics, there is a need to separate ‘Medialinguistics’ as an independent field, to create a theoretical basis for the study of the dialectic of media text and media discourse [16; 9; 28; 8; 11; 5; 26; 23; 29]. John Corner, a Briton, first described the subject and objectives of the new direction in his article The Scope of Media Linguistics. [27].

The establishment of the International Scientific Journal ‘Medialinguistics’ in Russia is a bright proof of our opinion. The journal ‘Medialinguistics’ publishes articles on general theoretical problems of scientists in new and promising areas of science, the place and role of linguistic tools in the media, the typology of media, comparative study of media language, etc. The journal undertakes to adequately cover the emerging state of modern medialinguistics as a part of linguistics, to fully cover the most interesting and important scientific approaches to media and media language in general. The journal collaborates not only with Russia, but also with influential representatives of the scientific communities of Belarus, Bulgaria, China, Poland, Turkey, and Ukraine [29]. It would be expedient for our Uzbek linguists to cooperate with the editors of this journal.

Components and levels of creation and distribution of media texts in the field of media linguistics include all linguistic and extralinguistic factors: linguistic-format features, functional genre classification, phonological, syntagmatic, methodological and interpretive features, cultural features, ideological modality, the influence of mass communication methods on pragmalinguistic value issues can be analyzed. The methodological basis of medialinguistics combines the achievements of all areas, such as discursive analysis, content analysis, cognitive linguistics, critical analysis, functional stylistics, linguoculturology, used in the context of media texts [23, pp. 610-616]. Thus, a very effective field of analysis has been formed to study the leading linguopragmatic features of modern media texts.

The leading object of medialinguistics, *mediatext*, is a dialectical unit of linguistic and media characteristics, a communication material created in a combination of semiotic characters such as language units, graphic image, audio and video, and it is relevant in the media discourse. That is, the text is considered as a product of discourse, the media text as a unit of media discourse, and attention is paid to the complementary and different aspects between these four concepts.

The term ‘**mediatext**’ was first used by TG Dobrosklonskaya in his book “Questions of the study of media texts: Experience in the study of modern English media” (“Mediamatn research issues: from the experience of modern English media research”) [10].

Consequently, the scope of the traditional object of the concept of text has expanded, and as a whole based on the semantic interdependence of units belonging to different semiotic features, it has acquired new infinite possibilities.

The term ‘media text’ refers to parallel or intersecting events that can replace each other – mass-communicative text, media text, journalistic text, newspaper text, teletext, advertising text, PR-text, Internet text, and so on. It should be noted that the semantic structure of the term ‘media’ (Latin ‘media’, ‘medium’ – method, tool) can be called any means of media – from rock paintings, traditional books, works of art to the most advanced modern technological

developments. [14, pp. 320-334; p.9, pp. 54; 17; 4]. At the same time, M. Yu. Kazak notes that it has become customary to use the term as a generalizing term in relation to media texts [21, p. 129].

Apparently, M. Yu. Kazak in the term *mediamatn*, in general, generalizes all the means of information that are presented illustratively, or more precisely, received by reading, seeing and hearing. In fact, paintings and inscriptions carved into rocks and rocks thousands of years ago are recognized as historical sources of information about the lives of the people of that time, or simple printed sources – books, newspapers, magazines – both visually and radio devices. is calculated. However, today the term ‘media product’ refers mainly to audiovisual means. It can be said that the phenomenon of narrowing of the semiotic area of the lexeme has occurred, i.e. only technical possibilities are considered as a means.

Mediatext combines media and verbal texts, in which the complex nature of language (creative material), the linguistic ability of the individual, the print media, the television channel, the means and possibilities of radio [24, p.130].

To date, the interpretation of the media world, i.e., ‘mass media,’ has expanded so much that it can no longer fully satisfy the researcher or the reader. The term ‘medium’, which passed from Latin to English, is no longer understood simply as ‘method’, ‘means’, because now the meaning of ‘information carrier’ is preferred. That is why the term media as a technological tool is actively used. It refers to the general content of media (transmitted through them), presentation forms (books, cassettes, movies, radio and television programs, e-mail, the Internet in general, print, blogs), and so on. In particular, internally divided networks are broadcasting (broadcast or electronic media) and print media (print, print media), as well as the blogosphere and social networks, i.e. a very wide field or media that has the property of combining knowledge and information transmission [20, pp.180-188].

In any type of communication, the affiliation of communicators to a particular ethnocultural group also leaves its mark on the choice of media. For example, for Uzbeks, the main dish is soup. As a combination of Islamic and national concepts, soup is distributed to neighbors and relatives on the eve of Eid. In the modern fast-paced life of society, although the roots of primitive ethnopsychological values seem to have shed some light, their figurative reflection in the minds of language-speakers continues to be preserved. Indeed, these figurative concepts are widely used in personal media discourse. This is a handy tool for communicators to understand each other quickly and easily.

Image 1 (media text).

Modern reputation ☺

- Today, 65 likes, 27 comments, 6 shares of my status in the network. How good is it? How is yours getting on?

“No better than yours.” I heard a thank you from my teacher once, the old man next door said “well-done”, and my mother hugged me kindly.

Image 2 (media text).

It is natural that paralinguistic tools serve to complement speech communication and increase its effectiveness. If we analyze the interrelationship of linguistic and paralinguistic units in this media text from a pragmatic point of view, some details ‘speak’. Initially, the title itself suggests that the modern interpretation of concepts is changing. The lexemes ‘like’, ‘comment’, ‘share’ in the text indicate that the addressee is now a member of the ‘nashavand’ community, who is devoted to Internet communication. It is also understandable that the first part of the dialogue belongs to the blonde girl in the picture, as her views are ‘modern’ and she herself is a typical representative of young people influenced by popular culture. The lexemes ‘teacher’, ‘old man’, and ‘mother’ in the addressee’s speech indicate that the speaker is being brought up in the spirit of national moral values.

Based on our observations, we have classified the main directions of research in the field of linguistics on media discourse and media text, which is a new stage in the development of public and private communication, as follows:

✓ *Meditext as an object of linguistic research* (D.Metison, V.E.Chernyavskaya, G.Ya.Solganik, T.G.Dobrosklonskaya, E.G.Shestakova L.I.Shevchenko, V.S.Djabrailova, M.P. Fomicheva, etc),

✓ *Media text in the media* (G.Kress, T. van Leeuwen, D.Machin, Ulla Carlsson, Sherry Hope Culver, I.V.Vysotskaya, N.E.Petrova, N.V.Bychkovskaya, T.R.Krasikova, E.A.Kojemyakin, Yu.A.Oganesova, O.B.Sirotnina, M.A.Kormilitsyna, S.V.Ilyasova, N.A.Kornilova, V.I.Jelvis, L.R.Duskaeva, L. A.Gulyuk, D.V.Ivanchenko, S.H.Shamaksudova, N.Muratova, E.Grizl, D.Mirzahmedova, N.Yahyoeva and others),

✓ *The role and importance of media in advertising* (EA Lukyanets, NS Dyagileva, IV Vorobeva, VI Nikolaeva, NE Gegner, M.Yu. Pitinova, B.Kh. Abdullaev and others),

✓ *Linguistic and methodological features of mass media* (M. Yu. Kazak. G.M. Shipitsyna, A.Bell, A.N. Vasileva, V.G. Kostomarov, E.A. Uvarova. B.V. Krivenko, M.Montgomery, G. M.Cherkasova M.N. Kryukova, S.V. Shaydorova A.I. Prikhodko, A.A. Aulova, L.Yu. Kasyanova. N.A. Beketova and others)

✓ *Linguocultural aspects of the media text and its role in intercultural communication* (Yu.A. Klimova, E.S. Abramova, A.A. Pokrovskaya, I.G. Dronova, A.A. Konstantinova, etc.)

In recent years, a new direction of mass communication has emerged, which is directly related to the Internet system. The fact that no research has been conducted in this area under the above classification also indicates the urgency of the issue. Traditional mass media products were aimed at an uncertain group of mass recipients, and addressee consumption was latent, i.e., a limited number of recipients' responses to transmitted information (as a result of speech influence) (such as letters to the editor, some interviews, reviews). The fast and convenient Internet allowed to quickly and discursively communicate certain information, regardless of the type of media. Thus, the emergence of the Internet system and its structure, *the blogosphere and social networks* has led to the separation of the concepts of **media** and **mass communication** into two networks as separate phenomena. While radio, television, print media, and fiction have been described as one-sided mass communication, i.e., indirect speech activity aimed at the addressee, the formation of Internet communication has given rise to a two-way mass speech activity process in the form of dialogue and polylogue. That is, now the addressee has the opportunity to engage in public dialogue with any group, on any topic and in any group, as well as to react actively to the information leaked to him by the media. This further complicated the communication system.

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